

Isonitroso-4-methyl-2-pentanone as an Analytical Reagent for Platinum(IV)[#]

P. S. MORE and A. D. SAWANT*

Department of Chemistry, The Institute of Science, 15 Madam Cama Road, Bombay-400 032

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In continuation of our earlier work on the use of isonitroso-4-methyl-2-pentanone (HIMP) as an analytical reagent in the spectrophotometric determination of metals¹, we report here the extractive study of platinum (IV) with this reagent. It forms a yellow complex with Pt in the pH range 0.8–1.2. The complex is extracted with n-butanol in presence of LiCl and its absorbance measured at 370 nm.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance spectrum of Pt^{IV}-HIMP complex in n-butanol shows maxima at 370 nm, where absorption of the reagent is negligible. The extraction behaviour of the complex was investigated in the pH range 0–10. Extraction was quantitative in the pH range 0.8–1.2, almost instantaneous. 1 ml of 0.1% aqueous HIMP solution was sufficient for quantitative extraction of 50 μg Pt. The absorbance increased till 15 min and then decreased on further heating. Nearly 1 ml of 10% LiCl was sufficient for clear phase separation.

Apart from n-butanol, chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, ethyl acetate and MIBK were also tested as extracting solvents. The Pt-complex in n-butanol showed maximum absorbance and hence this solvent was used for further studies. The colour intensity remained stable for atleast 54 h. The system obeyed Beer's law over a concentration range 1.0–50.0 ppm Pt at 370 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.51 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.056 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The composition of the complex studied by Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method was found to be 1 : 2.

Tolerance of various cations and anions was examined in the extraction of Pt^{IV}. The tolerance limit for the extraction was fixed at $\pm 2\%$ absorbance. In the determination of 30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Pt, 1000 μg of W^{VI}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{III}, V^{VI}, Co^{II} and Ru^{III}; 500 μg of Mo^{VI}, As^{III} and Pd^{II}, 250 μg of Cu^I, Ir^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Hg^I, Fe^I, Os^{III} and Rh^{III} caused no interference. Both Ag^I and Cr^{III} interfered seriously. 10 mg of chloride, bromide, chlorate, bromate, oxalate, urea, molybdate and 5 mg of iodide, iodate, fluoride did not interfere. Interference due to thiourea and thiocyanate was removed by masking them with formaldehyde and nitric acid respectively.

The method was applied for the determination of Pt in various synthetic mixtures, Pt-Ag alloy and Pt-charcoal catalyst. The results are shown in Table 1.

Experimental

An Elico pH meter and a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer were used. A standard solution of chloroplatinic acid (0.1 M) was prepared in double-distilled water with few drops of concentrated HCl and standardised². HIMP was prepared as reported in literature. A freshly prepared aqueous solution of the reagent (0.1%) was used. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

To a mixture of an aliquot of solution containing 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Pt and 0.1% HIMP (1 ml) adequate quantities of dilute HCl and/or NaOH were added to adjust the pH to 1.0 in 10 ml of final volume. The mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 15 min, then cooled and equilibrated with n-butanol (10 ml) in presence of 10% LiCl (1 ml). The absorbance of

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Pt IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES

Sl no.	Synthetic mixtures (μ g)	Pt found*
1.	Pt (200), Pd (400)	199.80
2.	Pt (200), Re (500), Ru (500)	200.00
3.	Pt (200), Ni (500), Co (500)	200.00
4.	Pt (200), Rh (100), Ir (100), Pd (100), Ru (100)	200.08
	Alloy/Catalyst :	Pt% : Found/(Reported)*
5.	Pt-Ag alloy	3.96 (4.00)
6.	Pt-charcoal catalyst ^a	0.98 (1.00)
7.	Pt-charcoal catalyst ^a	0.49 (0.50)
8.	Pt-charcoal catalyst ^b	0.99 (1.00)
9.	Pt-charcoal catalyst ^b	0.51 (0.50)

*Average of three determinations.

^aParekh Platinum Ltd. ^bHindustan Platinum Ltd.

The average of eight determinations of 100 μ g of Pt was 99.85 μ g with standard deviation 0.54 μ g and deviation from mean at 95% confidence limit as 99.85 ± 0.07 .

the organic layer was measured at 370 nm against the reagent blank. From the calibration curve, the amount of Pt was computed.

Pt-Ag alloy sample was dissolved in 1 : 1 HNO₃ and evaporated to dryness. The residue was extracted with distilled water and silver was precipitated as silver bromide by potassium bromide solution. Platinum was determined by the above method. The catalyst sample was dissolved in mixture of HNO₃ and HClO₄ (4 : 1) and evaporated to dryness. The residue was extracted with 0.05 N HCl, filtered and diluted with distilled water. Suitable aliquot was used for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of platinum by the above methods.

References

1. P. S. MORE and A. D. SAWANT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 984; *Anal. Lett.*, 1994, **27**, 1737.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", E.L.B.S., London, 1975.